

ISic0961

I.Sicily inscription 0961

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble (white)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

Intagliatella catacomb

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palazzolo Acreide, Museo Iudica, inventory 2271

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Στέφανος ὁ μακα[ρία]ς
2. μνήμης διάκονος
3. ἐνθάδε κίτε ἀναπαυσάμενος
4. τῆ δι μηνι Ἰουνίου
5. ὑπατία Μοναξίου
6. □ καὶ Πλίνθα □

Apparatus

Text of IG XIV

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492687

EDCS 39102214

PHI 140539

PHI 175479

Bibliography

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